

DESIGN, MANUFACTURING, TESTING AND SIMULATION OF FIBRE COMPOSITE LEAF SPRING FOR HEAVY AXLE LOADS

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SUMMARY: This paper summarises the design, manufacturing, quasi-static and dynamic testing and finite element analysis of glass fibre reinforced polyester leaf suspension for rail freight vehicles named Euroleaf. Comparison of finite element predictions to experimental results has given confidence in the use of finite elements for the design of composite springs and for performance predictions. The Euroleaf suspension have been mounted on a tipper wagon and tested dynamically at tare and full load on a purpose-built shaker rig. A shaker rig dynamic testing methodology has been pioneered for rail vehicles, which follows closely road vehicle suspension dynamic testing methodology. The use and evaluation of this methodology have demonstrated that the Euroleaf suspension is dynamically much softer than steel suspensions even though it is statically much stiffer. As a consequence, the suspension dynamic loading at laden loading conditions is reduced compared to the most advanced steel leaf suspension over shaker rig track tests.

KEYWORDS: Glass reinforced plastics, double leaf spring, finite element analysis, static testing, dynamic testing and shaker rig.

INTRODUCTION

The primary use of fibre-reinforced plastics (FRP) in automotive applications, with the exception of a few specialized low volume vehicles, has been in semi-structural or decorative parts. Use of composites in primary structural areas of the vehicle such as suspension and body structures, has been very limited to date. In addition to material cost, there are two overriding criteria to be addressed to achieve significant application of FRP materials in automotive structures:

- Proof of structural functionality and durability
- Development of rapid, reproducible fabrication procedures to optimise manufacturing economics.

Considerable experience has been gained in the aerospace industry in the use of FRPs, especially in the design of large surface, small thickness aircraft components. In these components the FRPs are subjected mostly to tensile and compressive loads. In contrast automotive structural parts such as springs are required to handle combinations of shear, flexural and torsional loads. Therefore, only a limited amount of aircraft industry experience with composites can be transferred to the car, truck or rail vehicle sector.

However, glass-fibre reinforced composite leaf springs for transportation have attracted a great deal of interest from many researchers. One important reason for this is that they combine strength and low density. A weight reduction of 60% could be obtained by replacing a steel spring with a composite one with the same function. Springs for automotive or rail applications are designed to store and release energy for a very high number of duty cycles, typically 10^5 to 10^7 . The low density and high elastic strain of glass fibre reinforced composite (GFRC) materials provides them with high specific strain energy capacity [1]. Thus, GFRC offers a more compliant suspension system that gives a more comfortable ride and minimises damage to the road or track. Another advantage of composite springs is their excellent fatigue life and corrosion resistance [2,3].

The economic constraints in a mass production industry such as the automotive business are however quite different from those of the aerospace or even the speciality vehicle business. This is particularly true in the potential application of high performance composite materials which hitherto have been primarily developed and applied in a cost intensive manner. The fact is that while the aircraft industry would pay a premium for the technical improvements offered by advanced composites, car and rail vehicle makers look to reduce product life cycle time and cut manufacturing costs. Though acknowledging the advantages of FRPs as alternative materials, the car and rail manufacturers are cautious about finishing quality, production rates, reliable engineering, design data and product safety.

As a result, it has been difficult for successful composite spring developments such as Guest, Keen and Nettelfolds (GKN) for the road sector [4, 5] and Messerschmitt- Bölkow-Blohm (MBB) [6, 7] on the rail sector to penetrate the automotive market and this mainly for the reason mentioned above. This despite the demonstrable advantages associated with the use of FRPs against traditional material such as steel for spring development:

- Weight savings
- Decrease of noise transmission and noise emission
- Reduction of number of components and linkages
- Reduction of dynamic wheel loading on the road/track
- Improvement of passenger comfort

The potential of glass fibre springs has been investigated in two Eureka collaborative projects designated Eurospring and Eurobogie [8, 9]. The former was involved in designing and manufacturing GFRC springs for road vehicles, up to 9 tonnes axle loads, and the latter, a leaf and bogie suspensions, named Euroleaf and Eurobogie respectively, for rail vehicles up to 23.5 tonnes axle load. The market for the Euroleaf suspension in Europe is in excess of 100,000 wagons. The leaf springs discussed in this paper are made from glass fibre reinforced polyester using a Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process, which has been specifically tailored within the Eurospring project [8]. RTM provides a great deal of flexibility for the manufacture of complex composite geometries, including the moulding of eye ends directly to final shape. Furthermore, the method has the great virtue of being able to lay-up and heat set the glass fibre pack (preform) before it is inserted in the mould.

Polyester resin may not have the ultimate mechanical properties of epoxy resin, but it is more suitable for thick sections, which give rise to high exotherm temperature. For land transport applications cost-effective materials and processes are critical. The objective of the work is to test and simulate the double leaf spring statically and dynamically to ensure that its performance meets the required specifications.

EUROLEAF DESIGN AND MANUFACTURING

The Union Internationale des Chemins de fer (UIC) limit for axle loads is 22.5 tonnes, but within the UK, a 23.5 tonnes axle load is allowed on the majority of the network. The only

way to match the existing spring stiffness and carry this load is to use a double leaf spring. In contrast, metallic leaf springs generally have 5 to 11 leaves because of the higher Young's modulus of the material. The composite double-leaf spring system has been designed to replace existing multi-leaf metal springs on freight wagons using the existing connecting components, as shown in Fig 1. There is no change involved in the design of the wagon.

The spring consists of two glass reinforced plastics (GRP) leaves with different curvatures to introduce a gap between them at the ends. The springs are designed to be 1200 mm in length at flat with a constant width of 114 mm throughout, compared with 120 mm for steel. For both leaves, top and bottom, the maximum thickness is at the centre, 52 mm and 60 mm respectively, tapering towards the ends. The total mass of the two GRP leaves is 26 kg giving a total mass for the suspension of 38 kg against 150 kg for the UK 11 leaves steel suspension. The Euroleaf top spring is connected to standard UIC shackles via integral eye-ends. From Fig. 1, it can be seen that the centre of the spring is clamped within a standard UIC steel buckle which sits in a recess on the top of the axle box. The mass of the wagon and payload is directly applied at the ends of the top leaf through rubber bushes inserted in the eye-ends.

Fig. 1: (a) UIC Steel parabolic suspension; (b) Euroleaf suspension; (c) Euroleaf Rubber damper configuration

The reinforcing E-glass rovings (Vetrotex) are assembled using knitting machinery to form a unidirectional glass tape of constant width (Culzean Fabrics). The parabolic thickness is then achieved by cutting suitable layers to length according to design. These are then heat set to manufacture a preform glass tape pack. A high temperature polyester resin (Scott Bader) is used as the matrix. The glass fibre volume fraction of the springs is about 48% [10]. The material properties of the unidirectional composites have been measured at IPM and Risø National Laboratory in Denmark and are tabulated in Table 1. To design a track friendly suspension, it is essential to have low friction between the leaves and to introduce a reliable and consistent source of damping [19]. Steel parabolic leaf springs are better than flat leaves springs because they only make contact at their end points. For the glass fibre suspension, we use a low friction nylon wear-end on the lower leaf and a steel wear plate on the top GRP (eye-end) leaf. Additional sources of damping include the material internal damping and an external rubber damper element (Fig. 1).

STATIC TESTING AND FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Static testing

The set up, methodology and results of the static testing and FEA simulation have been reported in [11] and are briefly summarised in this and next section. The Euroleaf suspensions were tested in the Instron testing equipment at the University of Reading. The set up of the Instron machine rig reproduces the shackle supports of a railway wagon, which is identical to the UIC specified swing links testing configuration.

The eyes of the top spring are connected by shackle pins to the shackle which allows the spring to flatten under load by moving around a radius of 125 mm from the fixed shackle pin centre. Strain gauges are placed on the top and bottom leaves of the springs in the fibre direction.

The knee point at which the top GRP leaf and the bottom GRP leaf come into contact is at about 15 kN vertical load or about a minimum of 5 kN below tare load depending on the retrofit steel leaf spring application. This feature allows friction damping at the eye end between the top GRP leaves wear pad and the low friction nylon wear end of the bottom GRP leaf providing damping at tare loading conditions.

The stiffnesses of the Euroleaf suspension before and after the knee point are 700 N/mm and 2000 N/mm, respectively. Static tests show that the springs can carry safely the specified 150 kN maximum load although this is highly dependent on the moulding quality of the material.

Finite element simulation of static tests

Finite elements software MSC-Marc has been used to calculate the stresses in the GRP leaves and to simulate the load-displacement curve. The composite was simulated as anisotropic elastic material with properties given in Table 1.

Table 1: Material properties of GRP used

E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	E_{33} (GPa)	G_{13} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ν_{31}	S_{11} (MPa)	S_{22} (MPa)	S_{13} (MPa)	ρ kg/m ³
35	13	13	3.2	0.31	0.05	>1000	16	60	1850

The FEA results agree well with the measured values. At 134 kN laden load, the maximum bending stress in the fibre direction predicted by FEA is 350 MPa. The maximum bending stress in the top spring occurs close to the eye end. For the bottom spring, the maximum appears near the clamped section.

The dual spring system is designed so that the top leaf carries higher bending stresses than the bottom leaf and this has been verified from both testing and predictions. The reason for this design choice is that, should the top leaf fail first, the bottom spring would still be able to carry the full load alone and allow the train to reach a base for repairs. Results from FEA also show that the Euroleaf bottom GRP leaf can maintain the gross vehicle mass in case of the top leaf failing by delamination and so this mode of failure is a safe one, as the eye end remains intact.

FEA results shows that when 134 kN vertical load (maximum load) is applied at the end of the bottom spring only, the maximum tensile stress in the fibre direction is about 600 MPa and the maximum interlaminar shear stress is less than 30 MPa, which provides a safety factor at least 1.5 over the static strength according to composite failure criteria for various failure mode [12, 13].

SHAKER RIG TESTS

Introduction

The dynamic behaviour of a UK HAA rail vehicle equipped with the steel flat leaves, UIC steel parabolic and Euroleaf GRP suspension was investigated on a dedicated shaker rig in the dynamic laboratory of Skoda Vyzskum in Plzen, Czech Republic. The shaker rig hardware design and testing philosophy and methodology and limitations are described elsewhere [14, 15, 16, 17]. The shaker rig testing campaign was part of the Eureka Footprint project [26], whose global aim is to reduce the impact of road and rail freight vehicle on the design and maintenance of the infrastructure through a better understanding of the dynamic interaction between vehicle and road/track. The first series of tests compared the dynamic parameters that characterize the suspensions with the quasi-static parameters measured in the laboratory. A second set of tests compared the response of the rail vehicle, equipped with either the steel parabolic or the Euroleaf GRP suspensions, to various track vertical alignments fed through the shaker rig hydraulic actuators. The vehicle response and performance was investigated using traditional ride quality parameters such as the chassis acceleration and displacement and dynamic loading.

Drop tests

The drop tests enable one to determine the sprung mass natural frequency (N_f) and the suspension critical damping (ζ) of a suspension dynamically, rather than quasi-statically. These are the main suspension parameters affecting suspension dynamic loading and therefore track damage [19, 21, 22].

The EU drop test methodology [18] for road vehicle was adopted, as there is no test method for measuring the critical damping dynamically for rail vehicles. Directive 92/7/EEC requires the vehicle to be dropped by 80 mm and the critical damping ratio to be resolved by measuring the exponential decay of successive peaks p_i, p_{i+1} of the vehicle chassis displacement or acceleration responses immediately after the drop event. The critical damping ratio is calculated via the logarithmic decrement (δ) as defined by Eqn. 1 and Eqn. 2. The natural frequency of the sprung mass is calculated by Eqn. 3 with τ_f the period of the oscillation response.

The natural frequency of the sprung mass is directly proportional to the square root of the dynamic stiffness (k_d) and inversely proportional to the square root of the mass as defined by Eqn. 4.

The dynamic stiffnesses of the steel flat, steel parabolic and Euroleaf suspensions have been calculated from the natural frequency results from the drop tests using Eqn. 4. Furthermore, the stiffening factor is calculated using Eqn. 5. The stiffening factor is a criterion for classifying track and road friendly suspension [23] and is defined as the ratio of dynamic to static stiffness, k_d and k respectively (Eqn. 5).

$$\delta = \ln \frac{p_1}{p_2} = \frac{1}{N} \ln \frac{p_1}{p_{N+1}} \quad (1)$$

$$\zeta = \frac{1}{2\pi} \delta \quad (2)$$

$$N_f = \frac{1}{\tau_f} \quad (3)$$

$$N_f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k_d}{m}} \quad \text{with } m \text{ the sprung mass (kg)} \quad (4)$$

$$Stf = \frac{k_d}{k} \quad (5)$$

$$DLC = \frac{STDEV F}{F_m} \quad (6)$$

The drop test was performed by dropping the actuators under the front axle wheels following exactly the methodology described in the DIVINE and Eurospring projects shaker rig campaigns [19, 20]. For rail, it is clear that drops of 5 and 10 mms are more realistic because these are characteristics of welded and jointed track respectively. Therefore, drop tests have been performed with simultaneous drop of the front axle actuators in 5 mm steps and the frequency of the induced vibration checked.

Drop tests analysis methodology

Fig. 2 presents an example of drop test for the Euroleaf GRP suspension with an actuator drop of 10 mm at tare loading conditions. The decay in the resulting vibration is measured on both the chassis acceleration and the relative axle-chassis displacement.

Fig. 2: 10 mm drop test plot for Euroleaf GRP suspension at tare. Note: Top right: Chassis acceleration signal response; Top left: Dynamic load signal response; Bottom right: Axle-chassis displacement signal response; Bottom left: Actuator displacement signal response

Calculation of natural frequency (N_f) and critical damping ratio (ζ)

The logarithmic decrement (δ) and sprung mass natural frequency (N_f) have been calculated using Eqn. 1 and Eqn. 3 respectively. Theoretically, a minimum of two peaks from the chassis axle relative displacement response is required to measure the natural frequency and critical damping ratio but four peaks gives a more reliable result [17]. However, on some drop tests, especially with the steel suspensions at tare, only a maximum of two peaks could be distinguished and these have been used to determine N_f and ζ by adjusting Eqn. 1 and Eqn. 3. The data from the axle-chassis displacement transducer have been used as this gives a better response signal as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Suspension quasi-static test

The suspensions were tested under quasi-static conditions prior to installing on the shaker rig vehicle. The suspension stiffness rates (k) and the static damping (D_s) at tare and laden loading conditions were recorded as specified by UIC i.e. width of hysteresis curve at specified loading conditions for D_s . The static damping and stiffness rates are tabulated in Table 2. The Euroleaf suspension has a knee point below the tare load and therefore, has identical k at tare and laden loading conditions.

Table 2: Suspensions stiffness rates k (kN/mm) and static damping D_s (kN) at tare and laden loading conditions. The loading conditions considered are the loading conditions of the HAA wagon over the shaker rig tests

Suspension Shaker rig Load	Steel Flat		Steel Parabolic		Euroleaf	
	k	D_s	k	D_s	k	D_s
Tare (27 kN)	0.8	10	0.87	3	2	2
Laden (LL3, 90 kN)	1.7	21	1.82	15	2	5

Drop tests results

The effect of varying the drop height and suspension loading conditions on the sprung mass Natural frequency (N_f) and the critical damping ratio (ζ) are shown in Table 3. Furthermore, Table 3 presents the calculation of the dynamic stiffness (k_d) and stiffening factor (S_{tf}) for each suspension using the corresponding natural frequency results from the drop tests.

Table 3: Critical damping ratio (ζ), sprung mass natural frequency (N_f), dynamic stiffness (k_d) and stiffening factor (S_{tf}) at 5 mm, 10 mm and 20 mm drop height at tare and laden loading conditions for steel flat, steel parabolic and Euroleaf suspensions. Note: nm: Not measured.

	Drop Height (mm)	Tare (27 kN)				Laden (90 kN)			
		N_f (Hz)	ζ (%)	k_d (kN/mm)	S_{tf}	N_f (Hz)	ζ (%)	k_d (kN/mm)	S_{tf}
Steel Parabolic	5	4.1	24.8	1.76	2.0	4.6	12.9	7.	4.1
	10	3.5	24.2	1.36	1.6	4.3	15.9	6.8	3.7
	20	3.5	23.6	1.35	1.6	nm	nm	nm	nm
Steel Flat	5	6.2	36.2	4.04	5.1	5.8	18	14.8	8.7
	10	6.3	30.1	4.12	5.2	5.7	19.4	14.3	8.4
	20	4.5	19.4	2.10	2.6	4.8	46.8	10.1	5.9
Euroleaf	5	4.6	11.9	2.26	1.1	3.1	11.7	3.4	1.7
	10	4.2	9.7	1.93	1	2.8	13.6	2.9	1.4
	20	4.1	6.9	1.80	1	nm	nm	nm	nm

The effect of varying the drop height and suspension loading conditions on the sprung mass Natural frequency (N_f) and the critical damping ratio (ζ) can be summarised as follow:

- All suspensions show that the natural frequency (N_f) decreases with drop height independently of the loading conditions.
- The Euroleaf natural frequency results decrease with suspension loading from tare to laden loading conditions and therefore follow the theoretical relationship between natural frequency and stiffness defined by Eqn. 4.
- The steel flat and steel parabolic suspensions natural frequency results also decreases with suspension loading although the theoretical relationship between natural frequency and stiffness (Eqn. 4) is partly observed.
- The critical damping ratio (ζ) decreases slightly with drop height for the Euroleaf suspension at all loading conditions.
- The steel parabolic suspension critical damping ratio is independent of drop height at tare loading conditions but increase slightly with drop height at laden loading conditions.
- The relationship of the steel flat suspension with drop height is complex as it decreases with drop height at tare loading conditions but increases with drop height at laden loading conditions.

- The Euroleaf suspension exhibits a fairly constant critical damping ratio over the loading range.
- The critical damping ratio decreases with load for the steel parabolic and steel flat suspensions. The rate of decrease differs between drop heights and is not constant for the steel parabolic suspension except for the 10 mm drop height.

The stiffening factor (S_{if}) decreases with drop height for all suspensions at all loading conditions. This is coherent with the natural frequency dependency on drop height and the relationship between the natural frequency and dynamic stiffness defined by Eqn. 4. The variations of the stiffening factor for each suspension can be summarised as follow:

- Euroleaf suspension has the lowest stiffening factor (1.1 at tare and 1.7 at laden loading conditions for 5 mm drop height)
- Steel parabolic suspension has a medium stiffening factor (2 at tare and 4.1 at laden loading conditions for 5 mm drop height)
- Steel flat plate has the highest stiffening factor (5 at tare and almost 9 at laden loading conditions for 5 mm drop height)

Track simulation tests

The UK freight acceptance route vertical alignment has been measured by the track-recording vehicle and one can identify sections of poor medium and good quality track. 1 km sections of BQ 2, 6 and 9 were selected according to the UK track quality bands (BQ) classification, which varies from bands BQ1 to BQ12. Each band has an associated maximum vehicle speed restriction. The simulated vehicle speed was varied between 22 and 160 km/h depending on the profile input. The vertical profile of these tracks sections were run through the actuators on the shaker rig and the dynamic response of the vehicle recorded. Both left and right rail unevenness were simulated with actuators at each axle.

Track tests analysis methodology

The vehicle response, or ride quality, to track vertical alignment input been assessed by the following three separate parameters:

- The vehicle chassis accelerations (VACH) generally used for rail vehicle acceptance tests.
- The axle to chassis displacements (DS), which is a standard measure of ride quality for road vehicles [19, 20].
- The dynamic loading produced by the vehicle. The dynamic load coefficient (DLC), which is generally used for road vehicle interaction and used during the previous shaker rig programmes within the projects DIVINE and Eurospring [19, 20, 22, 24], was calculated according to Eqn. 6. The DLC is defined as the standard deviation of the dynamic load divided by the static load (equal to the load of one wheel).

In Eqn. 6, $STDEV F$ is the standard deviation of the wheel dynamic loading response and F_m is the mean load (static component of the wheel dynamic loading signal response, which is equal to the static load on one wheel).

Furthermore, the Impact Factor (IF), which is also generally used for vehicle/road interaction investigation [19, 20, 22, 24], was also adopted. The impact factor is defined as the maximum dynamic loading measured over a track section. The impact factor is especially relevant for rail suspension as UIC specifies a maximum vertical load permissible on the track [25]. The results are reported as a function of axle load enabling the comparison between each various parameters.

Track tests results

The general effects of vehicle axle load, vehicle speed and track quality on the ride quality parameters are discussed in [16]. The work presented focuses on the comparison between the

Euroleaf GRP and parabolic steel suspension as it is considered the most advanced of steel leaf suspensions [17].

An example of the results for the axle chassis displacements is illustrated in Fig. 3 for the standard deviation (left) and maximum values (right) respectively for BQ2 (poor track quality) at 44 km/h and 66 km/h. Furthermore, an example of the DLC (left) and IF (right) results are illustrated by Fig. 4 for BQ9 (good track quality) at 107 km/h and 160 km/h.

Fig. 3: Standard deviation (left) and Maximum values (Right) of relative displacement chassis-axle (DSi) versus axle load over track quality band 2 at 44 and 66 km/h for steel parabolic and Euroleaf

Fig. 4: Dynamic load coefficient (DLC, left) and Impact factor (IF, right) versus axle load over track quality band 9 at 107 and 160 km/h for steel parabolic and Euroleaf

The trends shown by the results of axle-chassis displacements standards deviation and maximum values (Fig. 3) are similar. The steel parabolic suspension axle-chassis displacements are independent of axle loading at 22 km/h and slightly decreasing with axle loading at 66 km/h. The results for the Euroleaf suspension were more complex. The axle-chassis displacement increases linearly with axle loading at 44 km/h. However for 66 km/h, the axle-chassis displacement initially increase with axle load between tare and the first intermediate loading conditions (LL1) and then decreases with axle loading.

At tare loading conditions, similar levels of axle-chassis displacement were obtained with the Euroleaf suspension and steel parabolic suspensions but were higher for the former at laden loading conditions (Fig. 3).

The trends shown by the results of the DLC and IF values differ (Fig. 4). The DLC decreases with axle loading for both suspensions. However, the IF increases with axle loading for both suspensions. For good quality of track (BQ9), the vehicle speed does not influence greatly the results. At tare loading conditions, the DLC is identical for both suspensions except for the Euroleaf suspension at 160 km/h, which is 30% higher. However, the DLC is 11 % and 13 % lower at 107 km/h and 160 km/h respectively with the Euroleaf suspension.

The comparison between the Euroleaf and steel parabolic suspension for the IF results are similar. At tare loading conditions, the IF is similar at 160 km/h but is 40% higher for the Euroleaf at 160 km/h. However, at laden loading conditions, the IF is similar at 160 km/h but 10% lower for the Euroleaf at 107 km/h.

DISCUSSION

The three leaf suspensions have varying degrees of Coulomb damping (friction damping) which affect their dynamic properties. Previous work have shown that for leaf spring suspensions, the main factors influencing the poor performance of suspensions are high vertical spring stiffness and Coulomb damping which are strongly dependant on velocity and amplitude [27, 28]. Furthermore, to minimize dynamic loading, damping should be viscous and carefully tuned to the spring characteristics [29].

Both steel suspensions rely on friction between the leaves as their damping source. The flat steel suspension has a large area of friction contact between its flat leaves whereas the friction contact is only at the edges for the steel parabolic suspension. The Euroleaf suspension has only the edges of the two GRP leaves in contact via a low friction self-lubricating nylon wear end. Other damping sources (in the drop test configuration) include the internal friction of the GRP itself and the rubber bush inserted in the eye of the top GRP leaf.

The quasi-static damping evaluation presented in Table 2 gives an indication of the level of damping for each suspension. However, as the contribution of Coulomb damping differs between suspensions, the quasi-static evaluation cannot indicate the nature of its influence on their dynamic properties. The nature, consistency and reproducibility of the natural frequency and critical damping ratio results from the drop tests demonstrates that suspension dynamic properties are very much dependent upon the amount of Coulomb damping. This is emphasised especially at high loading conditions and low drop height where overcoming static friction to provide damping and low stiffness is unpredictable.

The above conclusion is reflected by the results of the natural frequency over the drop tests, which are lower for Euroleaf suspension especially at laden loading conditions. Furthermore, the critical damping ratio results of the Euroleaf suspension, relying the least on Coulomb damping, were lower but more consistent and reproducible. This was confirmed by a further investigation into the critical damping ratio nature through the analysis of the positive and negative peaks of individual wheel signal response from the drop tests [17].

The above conclusions agree well with previous road shaker rig measurements on air, GRP and steel suspensions [19, 20].

The ranking of suspension using the stiffening factor criterion agrees well with the natural frequency results. Furthermore, the stiffening factor demonstrates again the negative effect of high level of Coulomb damping on the dynamic stiffness of suspensions especially at laden loading conditions and low drop height where high frictional forces are not overcome by small input displacement. The stiffening factor results demonstrate that the Euroleaf suspension is dynamically much softer than the steel flat and parabolic suspensions at all loading conditions even though it is statically much stiffer.

The characteristics of the dynamic parameters of the Euroleaf and steel parabolic suspensions established via the drop tests can be directly related to the track tests results. The similar value of the dynamic stiffness (k_d) at tare conditions of both suspensions (Table 3) resulted in similar axle-chassis displacements at tare loading conditions (Fig. 3). At laden loading conditions, the dynamic stiffness of the Euroleaf suspension is much lower (Table 3). This resulted in higher axle-chassis displacement for the Euroleaf suspension at laden loading conditions (Fig. 3). Furthermore, the measured dynamic stiffnesses can be related to the vehicle dynamic loading as a function of track quality. As a consequence, the DLC and IF are

similar at tare loading conditions and at laden conditions lower for the Euroleaf suspension (Fig. 3).

CONCLUSIONS

The new type of testing methodology described here, based on adapting road vehicle shaker rig testing methodology, has enabled the evaluation of rail suspension dynamic properties. These properties can then be compared to quasi-static properties. The methodology also establishes the correlation between suspension dynamic properties and vehicle ride quality. Whilst these tests have been undertaken for leaf suspensions, the methodology is quite general and is likely to be equally applicable to bogie wagons.

Glass fibre reinforced plastics can be used for leaf suspensions and have been shown to possess properties, such as viscous damping and low dynamic stiffness, which are prerequisite suspension properties to be classified as being “track friendly”.

The concept of adapting the EU road “drop” for rail suspensions is being pursued further with a view to developing the EU “rail” drop test for vehicles in service. Further investigation of the shaker rig track tests and other tests performed is under way.

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REFERENCES

1. Daugherty, R.L., “Composite leaf Springs in heavy truck application”, *Composite Materials, Proceedings of Japan-US conference*, Tokyo, 1981, pp. 529-538.
2. Kirkham, B.E., Sullivan, L.S. and Bauerle, R.E., “Development of the Liteflex™ suspension leaf spring”, *SAE Technical paper Series 820160*, The International Congress and Exposition, Detroit, February 1982.
3. Tanabe, K., Seino, T. and Kajio, Y., “Characteristics of carbon glass fibre reinforced plastic leaf spring”, *SAE Technical paper Series 820403*, 1982.
4. Lea, M., Dimmock, J., “The development of composite leaf springs for commercial vehicle application”, *Proceedings of Conference on Fibre Reinforced Composites*, 1984, pp. 10.1-7.
5. Scowen, G.D., “Automotive components in fibre reinforced plastic - A Review”, *Institution of Mechanical Engineers International Seminar, Utilisation of New or Alternative Materials, Autotech 1985 Congress*, 1985.
6. Leo, R.J. and Lang, H.P., “MBB Bogie development”, *MBB transportation Germany, International Railway Journal*, February 1991, pp. 41-42
7. Leo, R.J., “Bogies for advanced passenger trains”, *Materials for Passenger Rolling Stock Railway Division, Institution of Mechanical Engineers*, London, 20 October 1987.
8. Eureka E! 888 Eurospring project, www.eureka.be

9. Eureka E! 1841 Eurobogie project, www.eureka.be
10. Chaplin, C.R., Mayer, R.M. and Rezakhanlou, R., "A new approach to composite leaf springs", *Institution of Mechanical Engineers International Seminar, Utilisation of New or Alternative Materials, Autotech 1995 Congress*, 1995.
11. Hou, J., Cherruault, J.Y., Jeronimidis, G. and Mayer, R.M., "Design, testing and simulation of fibre composite leaf springs for heavy axle loads", *Journal of Strain Analysis for Mechanical Engineering*, to be published
12. Rajendran, I. and Vijayarangan, S., "Optimal design of a composite leaf spring using genetic algorithms", *Computers & Structures*, 2001, 79, pp. 1121-1129.
13. Shokrieh, M.M. and Rezaei, D., "Analysis and optimisation of a composite leaf spring", *Composite structures*, 2003, 60, pp. 317-325.
14. Chvojan J., Cherruault, J.Y., Kotas, M., Mayer, R.M., Gil Marcos, M.N. and Václavík. J., "Dynamic investigations of freight wagon suspensions", *ICEM12- 12th International Conference on Experimental Mechanics*, Politecnico di Bari, Italy, August 2004,
15. Chvojan J., Cherruault, J.Y., Kotas, M., Mayer, R.M., Gil Marcos, M.N. and Václavík. J., "Dynamic investigations of rail suspensions using a shaker rig - Analysis of drop test". To be published.
16. Chvojan J., Cherruault, J.Y., Kotas, M., Mayer, R.M., Gil Marcos, M.N. and Václavík. J., "Dynamic investigations of rail suspensions using a shaker rig - Analysis of simulating track testing". To be published.
17. Cherruault, J.Y., "Rail composite leaf suspension development and testing", *PhD thesis, University of Reading*, in preparation.
18. EU directive 96/53, Council Directive 96/53/EC of 25 July 1996 laying down for certain road vehicles circulating within the Community the maximum authorized dimensions in national and international traffic and the maximum authorized weights in international traffic, *OJ L 235, 17.9, 1996*, pp.59.
19. Dynamic interaction between vehicles and infrastructure experiment (DIVINE), Technical Report, *OECD Scientific Expert Group IR6. DSTI/DOT/RTR/IR6(98)1/FINAL*, October 1998, OECD Paris.
20. Harris, L. and Mayer R.M., "GRP suspensions - A new possibility for buses", *30th meeting of bus and coach experts, Scientific Society of Mechanical Engineering*, Gyor, Hungary, August 1999.
21. Aurell, J., "On the influence of different suspension parameters of commercial vehicles on dynamic wheel loads", *Proceeding of the Inst. Mech. Eng, Conference on Dynamic Road loading*, London, 1991.
22. Cebon, D., "Interaction between heavy vehicles and roads", *The thirty ninth L. ray Buckendale lecture, SAE Technical paper Series 951*, 1993.
23. Cherruault, J.Y and Mayer, R.M., "Criteria for track and road friendly suspension", *E! Footprint project proceedings*, Brussels, May 2002.
24. Cebon, D., "Handbook of vehicle – road interaction", *Advances in Engineering 2*, Swets & Zeitlinger, 1999.
25. UIC specifies a maximum vertical load of 322 kN.
26. Eureka E! 2436 Footprint project, www.eureka.be
27. Cebon, D., "Simulation of the response of leaf springs to broad band random excitation", *Vehicle System Dynamics*, 15 (6), 1986.
28. Fancher, P., et al., "Measurement and representation of the mechanical properties of truck leaf springs", *SAE Technical paper Series 800905*.
29. Magnusson, G., Carlsson, H.E., Ohlsson, E., "The influence of heavy vehicles' springing characteristics and tyre equipment on the deterioration of the road", *VTI report 270*, 1984.